

Performance Analysis of Pruning Algorithm used in Topology Control in Wireless Sensor Network

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Abstract – *Sensor network have emerged as a promising technology with various applications where power efficiency is one of the critical requirements. To reduce power consumption, algorithms are used to construct network topologies with a small number of coordinators while still maintaining network connectivity. By reducing the number of coordinators, the average duty cycle is reduced and the battery life is prolonged. Three topology control algorithms are used to identify the coordinator node, device node and sink node. The coordinator node buffers all the packets for its associated device nodes so that these device nodes spend most time in the sleep mode and only need to wake up periodically to retrieve their packets from the coordinator node. Furthermore, all the packets sent out from a device node have to be routed through its coordinator. Thus the device nodes could have significantly lower power consumption than the coordinator nodes, which always have to turn on their radios to receive data on behalf of the device nodes. The different role decisions lead to various possible network topologies. Here connected network topology is focused to maintain network connectivity such that the sink node can send its queries to all the sensor nodes while every sensor node can report sensed data back to the sink node as well. In order to save power, it would be desirable to choose the connected network topology with the minimum number of coordinator nodes and maintain topology using energy level. When the energy level of a coordinator node goes behind threshold, topology maintenance policy is used to elect a new coordinator and redirect its entire node to its neighbor nodes or new coordinator.*

Keywords: *Topology control, Energy consumption, Self pruning, Ordinal pruning, Pruning distance, Sensor network*

I. Introduction

A wireless sensor network is a wireless network consisting of spatially distributed autonomous devices using sensors to cooperatively monitor physical or environmental conditions such as temperature, sound, vibration, pressure, motion or pollutants at different locations. Sensor network have emerged as a promising technology with various applications where power efficiency is one of the critical requirements. Sensor networks can bring a wide range of promising applications such as habitat monitoring, structure monitoring and battlefield monitoring. Since sensor nodes are always battery operated, power consumption becomes one of the tight constraints in sensor networks. The recent IEEE 802.15.4 standard offers a promising platform for wireless sensor networks. Radio communication such as transmitting, receiving and listening dominates the scarce power budget and determines the lifetime of sensor networks. It is well known that the idle mode consumes nearly the same power as the transmitting or receiving mode in wireless communication. Turning a radio to sleep mode becomes the key technique to save power.

Since the sensor nodes have limited power backup, it is necessary to control the topology through with the packets are routed or forwarded. There are many algorithms in the literature in which General pruning, Self pruning and Ordinal pruning are consider in this paper for performance analysis.

II. Related Work

Topology Maintenance

Span protocol [1] has been proposed to construct a set of coordinators based on clustering. A node becomes a coordinator if it has two neighbors that are not directly connected, indirectly connected via one intermediate coordinator or indirectly connected via two coordinators. The priority for assigning a coordinator node is computed from its energy level, node degree and the number of pairs of its neighbors that are not directly connected. A node changes from a coordinator to a non-coordinator when its energy level is low. However network connectivity cannot be guaranteed since two coordinators may simultaneously become non-coordinators. In [7], Reactive low overhead scheme (RLS) for topology maintenance has been proposed. For topology control, the

algorithm called distributed shortest path tree (DSPT) is used. Based on DSPT, the problem of topology maintenance in heterogeneous wireless sensor networks is addressed as some nodes fail. In RLS, nodes in immediate surroundings of a faulty node are first triggered to respond. If they could not ensure that the network is connected, the other related nodes are further triggered.

Selection of Coordinators

In addition to saving power, the topology control technique based on selecting coordinators can also be applied to avoid a broadcast storm. Rule K [5] has been extended to solve the broadcast problem, in which only the selected coordinators need to forward the broadcast packets. In the broadcast problem, besides neighborhood information, broadcast history can also be employed in selecting coordinators so that a node that has already broadcasted the message will be given the highest priority. The idea of using broadcast history is similar to the idea of waiting for the decision of some neighbors because both ideas depend on some decision orders among the nodes. However, in broadcast based approaches, the decision orders are mainly built upon the randomness in channel competitions, whereas in proposed algorithms, decision orders are well determined based on node IDs and hop distances. Thus SP, OP, LP algorithms [3] can be formally analyzed and proved. Furthermore, the SP algorithm tries to construct short routing path of the sink node, which will lead to a short end-to-end delay.

Topology Control

To reduce power consumption, network topologies with a small number of coordinators are constructed while still maintaining network connectivity. By reducing the number of coordinators, the average duty cycle is reduced and the battery life is prolonged. Three topology control algorithms are used to construct the network. Self-pruning (SP)[3] is the simplest one with $O(1)$ running time and provides the shortest path to the sink node. Ordinal pruning (OP) [3] is a tradeoff between the SP and OP pruning algorithms and has slightly higher power consumption than OP. Furthermore, all three algorithms are independent of the physical radio propagation characteristics. Although topology control algorithms can optimize the network topology, the resultant topology is usually changeable. So topology maintenance algorithm is proposed to balance the network still maintaining network connectivity.

In these algorithms, the average end to end delay time is increased because more number of coordinators nodes are present in the topology. Next by traversing more number of coordinator from the centralized node, the battery life is decreased. It results in the network connectivity problem. Therefore in this paper, we propose an algorithm which controls the topology using energy level.

III. Pruning Algorithms

General Pruning

The default role of each node is coordinator so that pruning is used to indicate the decision that a node is excluded from the dominating set. To provide an overview of the pruning algorithms, a GP is given below

- Collect two hop neighborhood information
- Build waiting list L
- If L is not empty then wait for role announcement from all the nodes in L
- If satisfying the pruning conditions then the node itself is a device node else the node itself is a coordinator node
- Broadcast its own role announcement

Different pruning algorithms are based on their different definitions of a waiting list, which is built upon the node IDs and hop distances. Each node runs the same localized algorithm and the whole algorithm stops when every node announces its role. The whole algorithms will definitely converge since the waiting list is carefully constructed on each node to avoid a deadlock. However due to the different sizes of waiting lists, the algorithm will have different convergence times.

Self-Pruning

In a sensor network, the nodes near the sink node always need to forward the traffic between the sink and the nodes far from the sink. Thus the definition for priority of a node to be a coordinator as follows.

If the two nodes have different hop distances, the node with a shortest hop distance has a higher priority otherwise the node with a smaller node ID has a higher priority. The first algorithm is composed of two tests. For each node v , let the set $S(v) = N(v) \cap \{u \mid u \text{ have a higher priority than } v\}$ where $N(v)$ is the set of neighbors of node v and $S(v)$ is the set of nodes of node v which satisfies the pruning condition. Node v will not be a coordinator if $S(v)$ is non empty and connected and $N(v)$ is sub set of $S(v)$ union $N(v)$. The first condition is called connectivity test and the second condition is called coverage test.

Ordinal Pruning

For each node, the SP algorithm reserves the shortest path to the sink node. However, the SP algorithm is not effective in reducing the number of coordinators. Since every node makes its decision independently, it does not consider the possibilities that some neighbors with lower priorities become coordinators. Having more neighboring coordinators could increase the change to pass the coverage test. If the set of neighbors with higher priorities is a connected sub graph and covers the whole neighbor set, the expanded set should still be connected after adding other neighboring coordinators. For each node v , let the set $S(v) = N(v) \cap \{u \mid u \text{ have a higher priority than } v \text{ or } u \text{ has a lower priority but becomes a coordinator}\}$.

$N(v)$ is the set of neighbors of node v , $S(v)$ is the set of nodes which satisfies the pruning condition. Node v will not be a coordinator if $S(v)$ is non empty and connected and $N(v)$ is sub set of $S(v)$ union $N(v)$. The first condition is called connectivity test and the second condition is called coverage test. Since every node decides its role only after all its neighbors with lower priorities have determined their roles, this algorithm is called ordinal algorithm.

Layering Pruning

The OP algorithm can reduce more coordinators than the SP algorithm since all nodes will sequentially decide their roles in the OP algorithm, but the running time in the OP algorithm is much longer. Let n denote the total number of sensor nodes. The running time of the OP algorithm is $O(n)$ whereas that of the SP algorithm is just $O(1)$. In order to obtain a tradeoff between the number of deleted coordinators and running time, another pruning algorithm called layered pruning [3] is proposed. Instead of waiting for the decisions of all the neighbors with lower priorities, each node just takes into account all neighbors with higher hop distances. For each node v , let the set $S(v) = N(v) \cap \{u \mid u \text{ have a higher priority than } v \text{ or } d(u) > d(v) \text{ but } u \text{ becomes a coordinator}\}$. $N(v)$ is the set of neighbors of node v . $S(v)$ is the set of nodes v which satisfies the pruning condition. Node v will not be a coordinator if $S(v)$ is non empty and connected and $N(v)$ is the sub set of $S(v)$ union $N(v)$. The first condition is called connectivity test and the second condition is called coverage test. Therefore all the nodes in the same layer decide their roles simultaneously.

Topology maintenance

First minimum numbers of coordinators are elected so that every node is in the radio range of at least one coordinator using topology control algorithms. When the energy level of the coordinator node gets behind the threshold value [6], the role rotation takes place to maintain network connectivity. Then the system elects the new coordinators using topology maintenance algorithm in order to ensure that all nodes share the task of providing network connectivity. Thus it attempts to increase network lifetime without loss of capacity or an increase in latency. The topology maintenance policy is as follows.

For each node v whose energy level is low

Identify the predecessor set of v

Identify the neighbor set of v

Select the nodes eligible to become device node such that eligible device = Neighbor (V) \cap Self pruning (G)

Nodes that have common predecessor in eligible device set is identified and if the energy level is high or hop distance is less than or equal to hop distance of v , then announce the result node as the new coordinator.

Direct the predecessor of v to new coordinator

IV. Performance Analysis

In a sensor network, the nodes near the sink node always need to forward the traffic between the sink node and the nodes far from the sink. Thus we define the priority of a node to be a coordinator as follows. If two nodes have different hop distances, the node with a shorter hop distance has a higher priority otherwise the node with smaller node ID has a higher priority. The decision orders are well determined based on node IDs and hop distances and energy level.

Three topology control algorithms used are Self pruning, Ordinal pruning and Layered pruning. Self pruning is the simple one and provides the shortest path to the sink node. Ordinal pruning can significantly improve Sp in terms of power saving. Layered pruning is a tradeoff between the first two pruning algorithms and has slightly higher power consumption than OP. The number of coordinators is more in SP when compared with LP but OP produces less no of coordinators than SP and LP. The comparison of distance between the nodes for the SP, OP and LP algorithms are also performed.

TABLE 1: COMPARISON OF PRUNING ALGORITHMS

Parameters		Self Pruning	Ordinal Pruning	Layered Pruning
No of coordinators		7	5	6
Distance	0-15	3	3	4
	0-13	3	3	4
	0-10	3	3	3

V. Conclusion and Future Work

Three localized pruning algorithms have been analyzed in this paper which is used for constructing energy efficient network topology in 802.15 based sensor network. For Sp algorithm with $O(1)$ running time, for each node, the generated topology maintains the shortest path to the sink node. Thus Sp provides the shortest average and end to end delay among the three algorithms. Op has significantly outperformed Sp in terms of power saving. Up to 60% coordinator nodes can be reduced in dense sensor networks so that the performance of the OP algorithm can match that of the centralized pruning algorithm. The average end to end delay is increased to around 10 to 15 percent. The major drawback of OP is its long running time $O(n)$ which is too long for large scale sensor networks. LP can substantially reduce the running time to $O(\sqrt{n})$. Power consumption and average end to end delay have both increased by just less than 15% compared with OP. With their different characteristics in power saving average end to end delay and running time, a flexible set of

topology control solutions has been provided. Different sensor networks can choose different algorithms based on their unique application requirements. First minimum numbers of coordinators are elected so that every node is in the radio range of at least on coordinators are elected so that every node is in the radio range of at least one coordinator using topology control algorithm. When the energy level of the coordinator node gets behind the threshold value, the role rotation takes place to maintain network connectivity. Then the system elects the new coordinators using topology maintenance algorithm in order to ensure that all nodes share the task of providing network connectivity. Thus it attempts to increase network lifetime without loss of capacity or an increase in latency.

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